

Study on preparation of asphalt antistrip additives from amines and aldehydes

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Asphalt antistrip agents have been prepared by condensation of formaldehyde with tetraethylenepentamine (TEPA), triethylenetetramine (TETA), diethylenetriamine (DETA) and ethylenediamine (EDA), respectively. Main technical parameters are optimized by orthogonal test. The study shows that synthesis in the absence of no solvents has the advantages of high yields. The additives prepared from TEPA and TETA have better antistrip properties than the ones from DETA and EDA.

Bitumen and aggregate materials useful for building of highways are well known. In order to obtain the pavement of high quality and strength, effective ways are to use acidic rocks (SiO_2 content of rocks $>66\%$) of high strength, and granite for good resistance to wear and skid. But the acidic rocks have poor adhesion to bitumen, thus leading to bitumen stripping. We have found that the addition of antistrip additives into bitumen greatly improves the adhesion between bitumen and acidic aggregate materials¹, and thus increase the life of the pavement. The present paper reports the preparation of such additives from amines (such as tetraethylenepentamine, triethylenetetramine, diethylenetriamine and ethylenediamine) and formaldehyde.

Results and Discussion

Preparation from TEPA: The additives were synthesized from TEPA and formaldehyde in the presence and in absence of solvents (methanol). The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2. It is seen that the quality of the products

prepared in the presence of methanol is not stable, whereas that without solvent stable (the adhesion grades reaching 4). And the yields of the products in Table 2 are higher than that in Table 1.

The reaction between the aldehyde and the organic amine or polyamine is usually conducted in the presence of an inert solvent. The solvent serves as a polymerization or oligomerization diluent⁴. But the addition of solvents makes reaction procedure complicated with increasing energy consumption. Hence comparing the experimental results (Tables 1 and 2) we considered that it was better not to use solvents.

Taking the stripped rates as the object function and the conditions such as molar ratio of reagents, reaction time and temperature as variable factors, we evaluated the effects of these three factors on the function, and optimized the three technological parameters by using the table of $L_{16}(4^3)$ (i.e. an orthogonal table of 16 rows (16 times of test), 3 columns

Table 1. Synthesis in the presence of methanol*

Sl. no.	TEPA/ CH ₂ O mol ratio	T °C	t min	T ₁ °C	t ₁ min	p Mpa	t ₂ min	AG	Y %
1.	1 : 1.0	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	82
2.	1 : 1.2	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	3	83
3.	1 : 1.4	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	82
4.	1 : 1.6	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	82
5.	1 : 1.8	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	3	79
6.	1 : 2.0	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	3	73
7.	1 : 2.2	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	3-4	71

*T = Reaction temp., t = reaction time, T₁ = dehydration temp., t₁ = dehydration time, p = vacuum, t₂ = time of vacuum pumping, AG = adhesion grades, Y = yields.

Table 2. Synthesis in the absence of solvent*

Sl. no.	TEPA/CH ₂ O mol ratio	T °C	t min	T ₁ °C	t ₁ min	P Mpa	t ₂ min	AG	Y %
1.	1 : 0.8	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	88
2.	1 : 1.0	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	86
3.	1 : 1.2	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	85
4.	1 : 1.4	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	82
5.	1 : 1.5	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	83
6.	1 : 2.0	<30	120	110-120 160-180	120 180	0.02	50	4	82

*Explanation same as in Table 1.

(3 factors : A = ratio, B = reaction temperature, C = reaction time), and 4 ratio levels 1 : 0.5, 1 : 1.0, 1 : 1.5, 1 : 2.0; 30, 45, 60, 75°; 60, 90, 120, 150 min⁵. The results are shown in Table 3. The results reveal that the ratio was the notable factor for influencing the stripped rates, and the effect of temperature was greater than the reaction time. The optimum conditions were as follows : molar ratio of amine to aldehyde = 1 : 0.5; reaction temp. = 30°; reaction time = 150 min.

It should be pointed out that, since we did not investigate the effects of dehydration and vacuum pumping on the reaction in the orthogonal test, the optimum conditions would require further perfection.

Table 3. Table of orthogonal test

Sl. no.	Factors A B C	AG	Stripped rates %
1.		5	1.74
2.		5	1.30
3.		4	2.26
4.		5	0.77
5.		5	1.25
6.		3	3.47
7.		4	2.09
8.	L ₁₆ (4 ³)	3	3.64
9.		4	2.17
10.		3	3.28
11.		3	4.38
12.		3	3.57
13.		4	2.57
14.		4	3.09
15.		3	3.14
16.		4	2.19

Preparation from TETA, DETA and EDA : As already indicated by the orthogonal test, the reagent molar ratio was the notable factor for influencing the antistrip properties of the synthesized products. Therefore, the antistrip additives were prepared from TETA, DETA and EDA by varying the ratio under the same conditions as TEPA condensation with formaldehyde (Table 2). The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of synthesis from different amines and formaldehyde

Sl. no.	Amine/aldehyde mol ratio	AG		
		TETA/CH ₂ O	DETA/CH ₂ O	EDA/CH ₂ O
1.	1 : 0.25	3	2	3
2.	1 : 0.5	4	3	3
3.	1 : 1.0	5	3	3
4.	1 : 1.25	5	4	3
5.	1 : 1.5	4	4	3
6.	1 : 2.0	4	3	3

Using the product (TEPA/CH₂O) synthesized by repeated tests under the optimum conditions and the product (TETA/CH₂O) of the ratio 1 : 1.0, we investigated the effects of the additives on the antistrip properties. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Results of boil test

Sources of rocks	Lingqiu	Lishi	Yuanping	Yuanshan	Lanxian
Si content %	65.06	66.46	73.30	68.48	65.16
(a)	1	1	1	1	1
AG (b)	4	5	4	5	5
(c)	4	4	4	5	5

(a) = No additive; (b) = TEPA/CH₂O; (c) = TETA/CH₂O.

Tables 2, 4 and 5 show that the additives synthesized from TEPA and TETA have better antistrip properties than the ones from DETA and EDA. The adhesion of bitumen to acidic rocks is greatly improved by addition of the products prepared from TEPA and TETA to bitumen, and the adhesion grades of bitumen to acidic aggregate are increased from 1-2 to 4-5.

Comparison of the IR spectra of TETA or TEPA and its product reveals that the peak at 3350 cm⁻¹ (NH₂) in the reagents disappeared in the products. It shows that the primary amine is gradually converted into the secondary amine (-NH-) with the reaction. The peaks of free CH₂OH are retained in the products at 1350, 1150 and 1010 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

Aggregate material used was local granite rocks employed in preparing pavement. The cube shaped stone size was such that it passed 19 mm sieve and retained on 13.2 mm sieve. The stones were washed in distilled water to remove all fines, dried at $105 \pm 5^\circ$ to constant weight and stored in airtight containers until required for use. Experiments were carried out with a commercial bitumen sample (Shell AH-90#).

Preparation: Formaldehyde (aqueous solution, 40% by weight) was added dropwise to a stirred reactor filled with the amines at room temperature. Since the reaction was exothermic, cooling was necessary to keep the temperature below 30° , reaction time being 1–3 h. The temperature was then raised to $110\text{--}120^\circ$ to evaporate water introduced with the CH_2O solution and kept at the temperature for 2 h. The temperature was raised again and kept at $160\text{--}200^\circ$ for 3 h to remove water and other volatile matter. The reactor was then subjected to vacuum treatment for 30 min at the boiling temperature. The final products did not contain any free formaldehyde.

Additives characterization: Among different tests for determining antistrip properties of additives², the boil test³ was used for evaluating the effects of additives on the asphalt adhesion to aggregate. The adhesion between bitumen and aggregate was determined by visual estimation of the stripped degree of the bituminous film on an aggregate surface after boil test, and given with adhesion grades. According to the standards of JTJ 052-93 (Table 6), adhesion grades are divided into 1–5 grades and the grades of 4–5 meet the specification's requirements. To increase the precision of evaluation, weight method was used in the boil test. The adhesion between asphalt and aggregate was quantitatively expressed with stripped rates:

$$\text{Stripped rates (\%)} = (W_1 - W_2)/(W_1 - W_0) \times 100$$

where W_0 , W_1 and W_2 are weight of the stone, weight of the stone covered with a coating of bitumen before boiling, and weight of the stone with bitumen after boiling, respectively. Boil test was carried out by using the Chinese Lingqiu granite. The addition of additives was 0.3% by weight.

Table 6. Evaluation of adhesion grades of asphalt to aggregate materials

Stripped degree of the bituminous film on the aggregate surface after boiling	Adhesion grade
The bituminous film is completely retained, stripped area almost being 0	5
Percent of stripped area of the bituminous film, <10%	4
Percent of stripped area of the bituminous film, <30%	3
Percent of stripped area of the bituminous film, >30%	2
The bituminous film is nearly completely stripped	1

Prepared additives were characterized by an IR spectrophotometer (FTIR-1730). Si content of rocks was determined by X-ray analyzer (TN-5400) and a scanning electron microscope (KYKY 1000 B).

References

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